

Being ignored is not the only possible form of social exclusion in human-agent interaction

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In a world where humans and technical agents (e.g., robots, AI) work collaboratively, processes of social inclusion and exclusion in human-agent interaction (HAI) gain importance. However, the current focus of social exclusion in HAI is too narrowminded and neglects many forms of social exclusion (e.g., averted eye gazes, microaggressions, hurtful laughter). To change this, the effects of different types of social exclusion will be explored in a series of experiments against the background of William's need-threat model [34]. By doing so, we will test the transferability of the model, build a HAI-specific taxonomy, and derive prevention strategies. We look forward to interdisciplinary discussions about this topic and hope to receive valuable feedback and inspiration for the presented PhD project which has just started a few months ago.

CCS CONCEPTS • Human-centered computing -> Human computer interaction (HCI) -> HCI theory, concepts and models • Human-centered computing -> Collaborative and social computing -> Collaborative and social computing theory, concepts and paradigms -> Computer-supported cooperative work • Human-centered computing -> Collaborative and social computing -> Empirical studies in collaborative and social computing

Additional Keywords and Phrases: social exclusion, human-agent interaction, human-robot collaboration, need-threat

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1 INTRODUCTION

Today's working environment is transforming into a hybrid world where humans and technical agents (e.g., AI, robots) are expected to work collaboratively [9, 22, 30]. For example, humans and robots can collaborate in

personnel selection [14, 20, 26] or manufacturing processes [2, 25]. Moreover, AI support teachers during exams [18], journalists during research [1, 4, 29] or physicians with diagnostics [27, 31]. The paradigm “Computers Are Social Actors” (CASA) states that people treat computers like human beings [17]. Unfortunately, this does not only apply to desirable behavior. People abuse robots [11, 12, 21], even in childhood [19, 35, 36]. Robots can be the reason for bullying situations among employees as well as they can initiate workplace bullying themselves [5]. It is also well known that robots [8] or AIs can be biased and therefore discriminate against certain people [13, 23]. While the discussion centers around terms like “abuse,” “bullying,” or “discrimination,” it ignores that these are only some forms of social exclusion. There are also other forms of social exclusion (e.g., dehumanization, microaggressions) which all entail severe consequences (e.g., alienation, depression, helplessness) in the long run [32] but have been neglected in HAI research so far. We will address this research gap by exploring various types of social exclusion in HAI in light of Williams’ famous need-threat model [34] to enhance prosilience and long-term robustness through human-centered design. In order to understand the broadness of social exclusion and to differentiate the forms of social exclusion from each other, a taxonomy is necessary, which we want to develop. We also want to engage in interdisciplinary discussion on how to prevent social exclusion in HAI.

2 RELATED WORK

There are plenty of definitions of “social exclusion” [3], with lack of participation usually being a core aspect [16]. In psychology, we often distinguish between ostracism-based exclusion (e.g., averted eye gaze, ignoring, silent treatment) and rejection-based exclusion (e.g., dehumanization, microaggression, hurtful laughter) [32]. According to Williams’ temporal need-threat model, ostracism triggers need-threat, which is reflected in a decrease in human needs (i.e., belonging, self-esteem, meaningful existence, control). If people’s need-fortification strategies (e.g., compliance, retaliation) fail, severe consequences (e.g., alienation, depression, helplessness) will occur [34]. Williams’ need-threat model [34] was mainly researched with the software “Cyberball” where players can be included or ignored in a virtual ball game [33]. In 120 Cyberball studies, need-threat has been widely demonstrated [7]. Some studies also proved need-threat when ignored by computers [10, 37] or robots [6, 15, 28]. However, other forms of social exclusion like averted eye gazes, micro-agressions, or hurtful laughter have not been explored in HAI yet. Nevertheless, we assume that all forms of social exclusion can cause need-threat and thus potentially harm users. For a safe, robust, inclusive, and trusted HAI, more forms of social exclusion and their consequences should be investigated and prevented during the development of technical agents.

3 OUTLOOK

It is crucial to ensure the (psychological) well-being of users and protect them from potential damage. Ostracism and rejection are just umbrella terms where it remains unclear what subforms play a crucial role in HAI. Perhaps some forms of social exclusion seem more severe in HAI than others. Some forms of social exclusion may not even be perceived as exclusive in HAI. There is a need for an HAI-specific taxonomy of social exclusion that considers human perception during HAI. Therefore, we will explore various forms of social exclusion in HAI in a series of experiments to compare effects, deepen understanding, build a HAI-specific taxonomy, test the transferability of Williams’ need-threat model [34], and derive prevention strategies. For this purpose, we will conduct vignette studies where subjects should imagine one form of social exclusion in HAI settings. We will vary the form of social exclusion and assess the subjects’ needs and need-fortification strategies with questionnaire items.

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